

Blueprint of the national and the Pan-European H2O Observatories

Preston Long¹, Margaret Renn Andrews¹, Rob Thwaites², Nataliya Kemenyash³, Tanja Stamm^{1,4}

¹ Medical University of Vienna, Center for Medical Data Science, Institute of Outcomes Research, Vienna, Austria

² Albion House Consulting Ltd, Marlow, United Kingdom

³ Data Science Institute, Takeda R&D, Zurich, Switzerland

⁴ Ludwig Boltzmann Institute for Arthritis and Rehabilitation, Vienna, Austria

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT: Authors declare no COI relevant to this work.

FUNDING STATEMENT: H2O has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 945345. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA and Trial Nation and JDRF.

DISCLAIMER: this article reflects only the author's view. Neither IMI, nor EFPIA, nor the European Commission, nor the JU are liable for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abstract

The purpose of the blueprint is to compile H2O approaches related to establishing and/or expanding the H2O model, developed within different work streams, and to provide guidance on how these can be applied. As new countries (etc.) are brought into the H2O network, this blueprint can help steer future collaborators. As we are already starting to expand beyond the initial four countries, it is critical that we have a documented approach that can be used not only for any expansion during the remaining years of IMI funding but also for the management of the growth of the network once this becomes fully independent. This deliverable includes three primary blueprints, 1) on the development of a new data collection site, 2) on the addition of a new technology provider, and 3) on the inclusion of a new H2O accredited disease outcome set.

Background

The H2O project will equip patients with tools to measure their outcomes in a standardised way, while giving them control of their data. It is the first-ever attempt at scale to collect and incorporate patient outcomes into health care decision making at an individual and population level.

The expanded H2O mission includes seven imperatives (see D1.1):

1. Empower patients;
2. Provide full control and ultimately full portability to patients of their outcome data;
3. Promote trust through an ethical governance of health data;
4. Ensure an ethical framework around access to health outcome data to advance science and health policy while respecting patients' rights to control their data;
5. Create an ecosystem open to all healthcare providers and patients;
6. Create transparency of outcomes to advance Value Based Healthcare;
7. Support evidence-based decisions on health policy.

From the outset, the consortium has identified and developed a number of characteristics that form the unique H2O approach that are also informative when considering expansion of the model.

- Health data is “regarded as a utility [that should be] available to all relevant stakeholders for the benefit of society.” (H2O Description of Action (DOA))
- Putting patients in charge of their data is at the heart of the vision. In H2O, “patients do not only collect outcome data, but also control, give access to and use their health data in a meaningful efficient way.” (H2O DOA) This is different from other approaches that create data for the benefit of clinical care and, therefore, patients, but do not allow patient control of the data.
- Building trust across all stakeholders is of central importance. There are three main elements to this: (a) agreement on clear governance principles that spell out the vision and mission of H2O; (b) establishment of independent legal entities with boards representing all key stakeholders in the health sector; and (c) introduction of a technology architecture that reflects and implements the governance principles in conjunction with a clear sustainability model to allow the overall H2O enterprise to maintain its independence.
- A focus on developing and managing an H2O ecosystem, open to all stakeholders, with incentives for data sharing, for scientific analysis and learnings, and for innovation and creativity through the data.

H2O country teams have founded the independent legal entities around which the National Observatory (NO) ecosystems are based in three countries (Spain, Netherlands, and Austria), with a fourth (Germany) to shortly follow, and focused on three diseases (IBD, diabetes, and breast and lung cancer). These entities will provide information for individual patients and their healthcare providers for use in clinical care. Data for both perspectives - at individual level and at population level - will provide meaningful insights to better inform healthcare decisions which will ultimately strengthen value based health care systems and will deliver better outcomes for all. These observatories are the initial examples of the larger H2O vision of a connected Europe.

NOs will operate under a governance model that guarantees compliance with data protection according to jurisdictional data protection law. The Pan-European Observatory (PEO) facilitates alignment and interoperability, guides expansion of the network, and promotes the benefits of measuring and using outcomes at regional, national, European and global levels.

The PEO and NOs offer an innovative framework to collect and analyse patient-reported outcome data accurately and precisely. National Observatories will be connected in a federated way to the Pan-European framework. Analytic queries will be sent to data-holders and aggregated results will be returned to the requester for further analysis to answer a specific question or to track an outcome.

We will actively encourage the model to spread to other countries beyond those involved in the current project by creating the governance of the PEO in a way that allows new organisations and national observatories to join. Key prerequisites for this expansion will be the willingness of new partners to ensure harmonisation of outcome (domain) standards as well as other outcomes-relevant data and adherence to the ethical and governance model for the management of data.

Implementation and expansion of the H2O model

New data collection sites

It is the overarching H2O vision that new national observatories will be established throughout Europe, united under the Pan-European Observatory, to revolutionise health outcomes collection and research opportunities. It is in our best interest to make this process accessible and flexible in order to enable this expansion, while also ensuring the integrity of the H2O model.

A number of resources exist to guide prospective sites, which are described in more detail under Section 3. Guiding principles and supportive tools. In short, a new observatory must uphold the H2O vision on health data and follow the agreed governance and data management principles. A location for the new national observatory must be designated and solid commitment is needed from relevant national stakeholders to support the observatory, including provision of resources to establish the new NO (though recognising that eventually the new NO will be a self-funding component of the H2O network). The structure of the national observatories is based on representation of the five main constituencies (patient organisations, society overall, medical professionals, regulatory bodies, private sector) within the board of the legal entity.

The PEO will be responsible for any decision on whether to accept a new member based on the following criteria:

- The organisation is, or will be, an independent, not-for-profit entity;
- The board of the organisation is constituted in line with Governance Principle A (see Section 3);
- The board of the organisation formally adopts the governance principles;
- The organisation adheres to the Constitution Agreement agreeing to:
 - Safeguard the comparability and consistency of outcome measurements in the interest of patients, society and science.

Adopt the Code of Conduct that is part of the Constitution Agreement and safeguards how the Observatories handle health data in the interest of patients, society and

- science.

Become a valuable contributor to the governing bodies of the Umbrella Observatory and contribute scientific and health policy expertise in order to advance the mission of the Observatory.

- A plan, agreed between the new NO and the PEO, is in place. This plan will cover the establishment and growth of the new observatory, including the commitment of at least one major academic hospital to be an active partner in the new observatory;
- The organisation agrees to adopt the technology standards of the H2O network, including for example a common data model (such as the OMOP Common Data Model), the FAIR data principles and interoperability standards such as HL7 FHIR.

Beyond the independent legal entity, the observatory ecosystem must have clinical site(s) ready to participate, including sharing clinical data; a way to collect and merge data, to pseudonymise/ anonymise/ aggregate data (depending on use case), ideally through an external backend provider; agreements with digital solution providers (apps) for administering patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) to patients; and method(s) to display data back to clinicians and patients (dashboards or similar) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. H2O National Observatory data ecosystem (see D1.9)

However, there are different ways to set up a national observatory in practice, and Annex I. National observatory case studies sets out specific examples from the first three NOs. Lessons learned from these NOs show the importance of a sponsor in driving forward the creation of the observatory and ensuring its initial establishment. It is furthermore helpful to view the NO as an ecosystem, where different partners contribute separate pieces of the puzzle, adding their own specific expertise. This format allows for better integration into present systems and fosters active ownership by stakeholders, optimizing likelihood of long-term success. Interviews with H2O partners and country implementation teams highlighted these five key aspects to keep in mind:

- Initiate the Observatory as a joint mission for all stakeholders;
- Ensure transparency and trust;
- Rely on internal and third-party experts;
- Learn from others and maintain flexibility in the approach;
- Leverage existing networks.

When establishing a new observatory, it is recommended to conduct one or more pilot exercises. The first one should focus on following the data journey and making sure that the data flow functions correctly. Such an exercise can be done with synthetic or randomly entered data as well as with volunteer participants. This test would help iron out some data flow issues prior to the first patients being recruited and ensure fidelity. Countries should start with a test run rather than go straight into full implementation (e.g. use dummy data or volunteer patients informed that they are part of a mock-up). This can be done with the existing capabilities in place, and will help unearth real issues in data and data flow in practice.

After that, it may be beneficial to conduct a second pilot, starting with a small group of clinicians and patients, and to expand first when any potential implementation snags have been resolved. Realistically, it will take time and coordination to get a new NO ecosystem working. Planning for stages, tracking progress against identified KPIs, and making adjustments where needed can mitigate potentially critical misalignment, and also helps to keep stakeholders on board. A Data Flow Maturity Model (Figure 2) was produced by the consortium to track this process during the project, and may be helpful for new sites as well.

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
	Initial	Basic	Progressing	Advancing
Outcome set collection/number of patients	H2O COS* collected; >20 patients per disease (incl. min. 1 follow-up)	>100 patients per country	>500 patients per country	>1000 patients per country
Primary data use for patients	Access to own PRO results (including longitudinal data)	+ averages from other patients	+ clinical data which are relevant	+ averages from clinical data from other patients
Primary data use for HCPs (clinical use)	PRO results available to HCPs	+ averages from other patients	+ integration in EHR	+ averages from clinical data from other patients
Secondary data use – data sharing for researchers	Access to COS* (PRO & clinical) data to researchers from the H2O consortium on site	Access to COS (PRO & clinical) data to researchers from the H2O consortium	+ researchers outside the H2O consortium	Same as level 3
Patient consent	H2O Consent**	H2O Consent	H2O Consent	H2O Consent
Diseases covered	IBD, Breast/Lung Cancer and/or Diabetes (minimum of 1)	Same as level 1	IBD, Breast/Lung Cancer and/or Diabetes (more than 1)	Min. one additional disease covered
Number of patient-facing technology partners	1 per country	2 per country	3 per country	4+ per country
Number of and type of additional sites	0	1-2 per country, including 1 outpatient/primary care	3-4 sites per country, including 1 outpatient/primary care	4+ per country, including 2+ outpatient/primary care
Independent patient utilisation	Possible	Possible	Implemented	Implemented
Patient portability	Possible	Possible	Implemented	Implemented
Linkability to existing data sources	-	Possible	Possible	Implemented

*COS = Core Outcome Set, includes PRO and clinical data; **adjusted nationally to local legal and ethical requirements

Figure 2. H2O Data flow maturity model

Expansion to new sites within a country that is already member of H2O follows the same principles as setting up a new observatory, and it will largely depend on the specific construction in that country. The new site will also need to commit to the H2O vision and principles (including using patient-reported outcome (PRO) data in patient dialogue, sharing EHR data, agreeing the data flow approach). Beyond this, it is a matter of ensuring resources, stakeholder buy-in, and data interoperability.

Expansion by linking with existing registries or other data repositories with identifiable data should follow based on patient consent. This will be more extensively explored and described towards the end of the H2O project.

New technology partners

A key factor in the success of H2O will be the use of technology to allow patients to monitor their outcomes in a way that engages and retains patients' interest. This is fundamental, as without creating value for patients and clinicians at the level of care delivery, sustainable data collection will not be enabled – and secondary use-cases for aggregated anonymised data will not materialise.

Many commercial solutions already exist for patients to manage and track their health, and it is furthermore clear that there is no “one size fits all” solution. Every patient has individual desires and functionality requirements. This is also true for routine electronic PRO (ePRO) assessment tools used in healthcare, clinical health record (HER / EMR), and data management systems. Numerous tools are already used even within individual centres. Therefore, the priority for ensuring H2O technological sustainability is to uphold basic criteria related to functionality, scalability, and security, and to partner with existing digital solutions that meet these criteria. The process for partnering with new digital solutions has been extensively analysed and tested within WP2 of H2O (Figure 3).

H2O process for selection & qualification of digital solutions

Figure 3. Process for approval of digital solutions

The partnership model (Figure 4) creates synergies and adds value for patients and healthcare professionals by establishing links with parties who have demonstrated success and allowing for customisation at different levels from individual patients all the way to systems. NOs or individual sites may take advantage of these vetted providers to build a more robust network without a need for internal development. Indeed, the preference and ultimate goal would be to move away from in-house solutions for PRO collection to an open ecosystem with multiple providers.

Figure 4. Technology partnerships

H2O offers compelling reasons for technology providers to partner with H2O. Full stakeholder value propositions have been detailed in D1.7, but as the diagram in Figure 5 below shows, there are nine main areas that make partnership with H2O attractive.

Figure 5. Value proposition for technology partners

WP2 followed a structured approach and process to exploring partnerships with discrete stages (Figure 6). Firstly, we published a Request for Expressions of Interest (RFEI) which described the H2O initiative and what we are seeking in partnership. We targeted directly organisations which we believed had solutions of relevance and distributed broadly via various channels. We held a webinar to provide more background and address any questions which was attended by ~67 organisations. Following this, we received ~35 expressions of interest. We triaged these respondents and proceeded to exploratory discussions with ~25 organisations (Exploration phase) – where the objective was to understand their business, value proposition, and track record, as well as at a high-level their interest and motivation to partner with H2O.

Secondly, we prioritised 11 organisations to hold more substantive partnership discussions (Alignment phase) with the objective to build trust, allow them to better understand H2O, and surface synergies that could form the basis of a mutually beneficial partnership. We also created a 'rights and responsibilities' draft document as the basis of our second interaction in this phase. During this phase several organisations dropped out of the process for varying reasons, and the dialogue progressed at varying paces with different organisations. Thirdly, we are currently driving towards agreeing partnerships with a sub-set of committed organisations (Execution phase).

Of these, most are patient- and clinician-facing outcomes capture solutions (Promptly Health, Heartbeat Medical, Kaiku Health, My Clinical Outcomes, and myIBDCare), however data infrastructure platform solutions are also included (Philips HealthSuite and Patients Know Best).

H₂O | Overview of approach and progress

Construct a constellation of win-win partnerships to **accelerate** and **scale** the H₂O health data ecosystem

Figure 6. Overview of H₂O technology partner selection process

It is recognised, however, that different national and site-specific needs influence the choice of technology provider(s). The networks within the first national observatory ecosystems include mixtures of in-house and commercial tools, which have all been evaluated according to the H₂O process (Figure 3). This mixed model may be necessary for newly established observatories or for new sites, however the long-term aim is to enable widespread use of many (approved) providers. This model gives patients and healthcare providers the choice and flexibility to meet individual requirements.

New outcome sets

H₂O's vision is to empower patients to measure their outcomes in a standardised way, enable shared decision-making between patients and clinicians and create a body of evidence through the data that will advance health science and policy. In order for healthcare systems and patients to derive full benefit from a culture of shared decision-making and create a true learning healthcare system, it is critically important to ensure consistency and harmonisation in the standards used.

Extending H₂O to new disease areas through the endorsement of externally developed outcome sets and the update of existing outcome sets in line with the latest scientific and health policy developments is preferred over the wholesale creation of new sets. H₂O aims to create partnerships and synergies with other key players in outcomes research, as opposed to competing and duplicating present efforts and standards.

Process.

1. A request is to be submitted to the Board of Directors of the H₂O PEO by any stakeholder who is willing to support the extension of H₂O to new disease areas. NOs, technology partners, private sector entities, regulators, patient organisations or any other healthcare stakeholder with a legitimate interest can submit such a request and provide the necessary financial support needed to carry out the process.
2. The PEO may appoint one or more NOs to process the request.

3. The NO(s) will appoint two Process Leaders (one from the private sector, one from the public sector) who will assign independent Fellows to the Task Force as a multidisciplinary expert panel to manage the request. The Task Force will include disease experts (from at least from two countries), patients or patient representatives (at least two), methodologist(s) with expertise in clinical outcome assessment and patient-reported outcomes, and other fellows as appropriate.
4. A rapid literature review is to be conducted by the Task Force to identify existing Core Outcome Sets (COSs) in the given disease (ongoing projects need to be considered as well).
5. The Task Force will assess existing COSs as per the following criteria,
 - It was developed through a multi-stakeholder (including patients or patients' representatives), multiple-round Delphi procedure. Broad stakeholder involvement in the process (including HTA, payer, and industry) is an advantage.
 - Characteristics and definitions of the outcome domains/concepts/constructs must be provided.
 - The candidate COS must at least define outcome domains. Measurement instruments (e.g. PROMs or clinical scales) could also be included.
 - Frequency of measurement must be defined (the frequency of measurements should be defined and periodically evaluated for practicality in medical consultation and adequacy of patient information collection).
 - Patient population is well defined and appropriate.
 - The candidate COS must have clinical practice as the intended context of use. Dual applicability for clinical research and routine care delivery is an advantage.
 - Outcome measures must have followed a state-of-the-art methodology (e.g. COSMIN, COMET-COS, ICHOM, OMERACT or comparable) and consider the standard of care therapeutic approaches.
 - The initial qualitative validation study is not older than 5 years.
 - The candidate core outcome set must be digitally implementable. The outcome set should be open access. Alternatively, a royalty-free agreement may be possible.
6. If there is more than one COS that satisfies the criteria listed in paragraph 5, the Task Force will select the COS that is most likely to take into consideration the latest scientific developments in the respective disease and provide a practical way of digital implementation in clinical practice. If appropriate, the Task Force may initiate a working group with the developing organisation of the existing COS in order to jointly agree on what should be the COS to be implemented in the H2O ecosystem. The Task Force will provide a structured and detailed rationale for their decision.
7. If the validation study of the selected COS is older than 5 years or there have been significant scientific developments, the assigned Task Force will contact the developer organisation of the existing COS and ask if the COS is still relevant or if a revision is planned, necessary or desirable. If so, the Task Force will recommend the NO(s)/PEO collaboration with the developer organisation of the existing COS to improve it as necessary.
8. If the developer organisation of the existing COS does not see a need to revise it, the Task Force will recommend the assessment of the COS for the endorsement by H2O or possibly the development of a COS in collaboration with a relevant standardisation organisation and implementation in the H2O ecosystem.
9. After the assessment of the candidate COS as per criteria in item 5 above, the Task Force provides a recommendation to the NO(s)/PEO on endorsement or not endorsement of the COS by H2O and underlying rationale. The PEO will maintain a COS database(s), provide the results of the assessment and recommendation.

See Annex II. New outcome sets for further details on creating new sets.

Guiding principles and supportive tools

Establishing observatories and expanding the H2O model, and thus increasing the size and therefore the power of the data, is a main goal. From a certain perspective, all project work and deliverables can be relevant to these efforts, and guidelines may be modified as the project continues. The following deliverables may be particularly helpful for expansion:

- D1.1 Observatory business architecture
- D1.2 and D1.9 Data Management Plans 1 & 2
- D1.5 Information governance and ethics framework
- D1.7 Stakeholder value propositions and sustainability success factors
- D1.8 Initial business model
- D2.2 Architecture blueprint
- D6.1 Overarching operational plans for national observatories
- D6.3 Operational Plan for the Pan-European Umbrella Observatory
- D6.12 H2O exploitation and sustainability strategy
- Scientific publications on the methods and resulting COS for the first H2O diseases

H2O governance principles

The full governance principles have been published in D1.1 Observatory business architecture.

- A. We will set up one Health Outcome Observatory per country.
- B. The Health Outcome Observatories will only be truly impactful if there is consistency in the measurements, the possibility to make comparisons, the ability to conduct analysis on large data sets, but also and most importantly strong trust in the Observatory by society overall and by stakeholders, including patients, citizens, regulators, HCPs, researchers, and industry.
- C. The emphasis of H2O is to enable patients to measure patient reported outcomes (PROs). However, the value of the data not only for individual patients and their clinicians but also for health policy and scientific analysis will be significantly enhanced if the H2O tools also incorporate an extract of important clinically captured outcomes.
- D. The Health Outcome Observatories will only succeed if there is sustainability in the model while at the same time a robust and ethical governance model for access to data that will build trust with patients and society.
- E. Health Outcome Observatories need to ensure that patients receive clear value from the Observatory, consent to the data collection and are fully appreciative of the scope and objectives of the Observatories.
- F. Health Outcomes Observatories will publish regular reports on the status of outcomes in the various diseases in order to promote transparency of outcomes, to support the health authorities in managing healthcare, and to advance science in the disease areas of focus
- G. Health Outcome Observatories will leverage technologies in order to collect patient reported outcomes and will create an ecosystem that encourages state of the art solutions for patients.
- H. The ultimate objective of the H2O is to measure outcomes in all disease areas, including co-morbidities. However, there is a need for prioritization in order to decide on the roll-out. Decisions on prioritization will be made within the Umbrella Observatory in collaboration with experts and the national Observatories in order to ensure consistency of measurements going forward.
- I. The Observatories will focus on measuring outcomes according to internationally accepted standards of health outcomes (both what to measure and how). Where no standards exist, the Observatories will introduce and commission an objective process for creating such standards.

Patient Agreement

H2O is committed to putting patients in control of their data and empowering their active participation in and contribution to their own care decisions, healthcare research, and systems changes (subject to their personal desire and consent). In order to achieve this shift in practice, we have developed a Patient Agreement to be implemented in the apps used to collect PROs. This agreement contains the H2O privacy notice and service terms, but it is much more than that. Patients can give consent and it is expected that they will be able to tailor their data collection and sharing preferences, as well as withdrawal at any time. See Annex II for the full Patient Agreement and H2O Privacy Notice.

It is important to note here that different countries have different cultural and professional norms and practices, if not legal structures. Some of the aspects of the H2O patient agreement will be regulated by the coming European Health Data Space (EHDS) legislation. However, initial implementation at clinical sites may require additional approval by internal Ethical or Institutional Review Boards. Additional local consent forms may be required.

Core Outcome Sets

A major component of the work in the first half of the H2O project was to develop standardised outcomes sets for the first four disease areas. A generic set has also been created, and now a pragmatic set. Following an international Delphi exercise, the consortium established a multi-stakeholder method for developing and agreeing these (See Annex II). This method can be applied when other disease areas are considered for inclusion in H2O, although it is preferred to endorse or update existing sets, as described above in Section 2.3.

The following sets exist.

Lung Cancer

de Rooij BH, van den Hurk C, Smaardijk V, Fernandez-Ortega P, Navarro-Martin A, Barberio L, et al. **Development of an updated, standardized, patient-centered outcome set for lung cancer.** *Lung Cancer*. 2022 Nov;173:5-13. doi: 10.1016/j.lungcan.2022.08.021. Epub 2022 Sep 5.

Metastatic Breast Cancer

de Ligt KM, de Rooij BH, Hedayati E, Karsten MM, Smaardijk VR, Velting M, et al. *International development of a patient-centered core outcome set for assessing health-related quality of life in metastatic breast cancer patients.* **Breast Cancer Res Treat.** 2023 Jan. doi: 10.1007/s10549-022-06827-6

The MBC set has been accredited by ICHOM and can also be found at ICHOM Connect.

Inflammatory Bowel Disease

(scientific publication under review)

Diabetes

(scientific publication under review)

Generic Set

(scientific publication under review)

Multiple Myeloma

(under development and discussion with ICHOM regarding accreditation)

Data architecture and data flows

Each country and site of the H2O project has slightly differing data architecture and data flow journeys. This variability is inherent to the real-world setting of the project and its scope, as the resources, legislation, and current architecture in place at each location are not identical. The patient-facing applications used, the EHR systems in place, and the back-end controllers vary from partner to partner (see Annex I. National observatory case studies). However, all systems constructed share several guidelines and objectives. The key components ubiquitous to all H2O sites are scalability as well as flexibility, privacy / security, and user-friendliness. At present, the project's feasibility study is underway and will test the four factors noted above in a standardised manner. Following completion of the study, a formal report and scientific publication of the findings will be released informing on the trouble-areas identified and the recommended resulting solutions.

Furthermore, the input and query of data must function efficiently for ten patients as well as ten-thousand. The bridging tech solutions used should remain open-choice, thus creating an ecosystem of growth and inclusion. See Annex IV. for illustrated data flow scenarios.

Business Model

Full models and accompanying details have been published in D1.8 H2O Initial Business Model. See also D1.7 Stakeholder value propositions and sustainability success factors.

In order to set up H2O and its component parts as a sustainable, independent network, we have designed a business model that describes the financial and operating relationships between the parties involved in the network (Figure 8). The H2O business models are built upon the principles of creating value from data through collaboration and innovation. By working together, stakeholders within healthcare can leverage the power of data to improve patient outcomes and create a more efficient and effective healthcare system. This data must be of high quality, interoperable and permitted for distributed analysis at regional, national and European levels, offering unique insights that can benefit patients and many other health system and research stakeholders.

This will be ensured by the data quality work stream with H2O.

- **Business Model 1:** Primary patient-centred data use, with the national observatory and local network as central focus
- **Business Model 2:** Secondary data use (data based innovation) on the European Level, with the PEO and multinational H2O network as central focus

Underlying principles:

- Patient-centeredness
- Data Demand and Supply in H2O
- Think wider than H2O
- Diversified and holistic H2O value proposition
- Collaboration and partnerships
- Privacy and security
- Mutualisation and subsidiarity

The value chains (Figure 7) for both business cases have been further explored as a basis for completing the Business Model Canvas, which creates business models based on the three areas of feasibility, viability, and desirability.

Figure 7. H2O Data Value Chain 1: Primary patient-centered data use, with the national observatory and local network as central focus

Figure 8. Business Model 2: Secondary data use (data-based innovation) on the European Level, with the PEO and multinational H2O network as central focus

Conclusion

The project continues to grow and evolve. Tracking its growth and its barriers has shed light on the diversity of the H2O ecosystem. By mapping the current observatories, our data collection sites, and the in-development accreditation process for new outcomes sets, novel use cases have been created. The need for flexibility and long-term tracking is clear for the creation of new partner countries and data collection sites. Due to the level of variation possible in the structures, oversight and communication is crucial to ensure that the core objectives and 'must-haves' of the H2O vision/purpose are fulfilled. Similarly, the accreditation of new outcome-sets must adhere to the principals of H2O while acknowledging the numerous techniques used around Europe and various institutions. A more rigid guideline for development can be used for collaborators who intend on working with H2O prior to the start of the new outcomes set development. However, the quality indicators and requirements for soundness of existing sets, developed with or without prior knowledge of the H2O's existence, must be considered. The three reported blueprints in this document should be used as dynamic case studies to reduce the burden of development for any future partners by highlighting lessons learned and pitfalls to avoid, and importantly to offer options and plans for developments. Finally, a key difference to consider with the H2O blueprint, as compared to that of a building for example, is that H2O is not static and never stops being built. Thus, the blueprints themselves should not become static documents, and they too should undergo review for possible improvements at a practical interval.

ANNEX I. National observatory case studies

[Content included from country teams and internal WP6 discussions]

Spain

Figure 1. Spanish legal entity composition

Figure 2. Spanish implementation structure

Figure 3. Spanish first iteration of the network

Netherlands

Figure 1. Dutch observatory structure

Figure 2. Dutch implementation structure

Figure 3. Dutch first network infrastructure: breast cancer
 Dutch H2O infrastructure - Breastcancer

Figure 4. Dutch first network infrastructure: lung cancer 1
 Dutch H2O infrastructure - Lungcancer

Figure 5. Dutch first network infrastructure: lung cancer 2
 Dutch H2O infrastructure - Lungcancer

Austria

Figure 1. Austrian observatory ecosystem

Figure 2. Austrian implementation structure

Ziel 3 - Vision

Germany

Figure 1. German observatory structure (proposed)

ANNEX II. H2O Patient Agreement

The below image is a mock-image of the H2O landing page. Please consult the actual text for titles of each box a patient can choose from.

This remains subject to technical feasibility and localization.

(A) I agree to register with the H2O patient network, to collect my self reported data for my own use, and for H2O to include my data in aggregated and anonymised comparisons of outcomes experienced by similar patients

*

Why we collect your self reported data from you

As part of the H2O patient network, you can use the H2O App to collect your self reported data (as defined here) on a regular basis. Your self reported data includes your outcomes and health data that are related to your health outcomes reported by you, such as:

- your current health
- the severity and symptoms of the disease you have that is being monitored
- your quality of life, such as how active you can be, if you experience pain, have breathlessness, about your appetite, bowel movements, sleep, level of anxiety or distress
- the extent to which you are comfortably able to perform your daily activities
- tracking any improvements that have occurred through the use of your medication, following operations or other health care treatments you have received
- data from your smart watches, wearables, or other of your devices, or any of your personal preferences

You may find it helpful to compare your self reported data with the aggregated and anonymised data of a pool of similar patients. H2O is keen to analyse this information from as many patients in our network as possible, in an anonymised way, in order to produce the most accurate comparison data for patients to use.

This combined anonymised data can also help health systems to improve the quality of the healthcare services they provide. H2O can use this data, also only in an anonymised form, to help the regulatory agencies that approve new treatments to understand which health conditions do not have very effective treatments today and need better alternatives. We are careful to only provide this information to organisations working to deliver or manage health services, to improve service quality or to conduct research to develop new solutions for health and care and which may ask H2O for analysis of anonymised and aggregated data. Please find here a link to our public register of approved research organizations [HYPERLINK:] ALL RECIPIENT ORGANIZATIONS.

We want to ensure that the self reported data that you have collected over time remains accessible to you wherever you live within Europe. To do this H2O needs to store a copy of some of your data. This includes your personal details, your self reported data and your unique H2O code number. This may also include your clinical data, if you agree to that separately in the following sections of your Patient Agreement. If H2O holds a copy of your data, you can change the H2O App that you use, or the healthcare provider with which you share your data, for example if you move within your country or to another European country, whilst always having access yourself to all your H2O held data.

How we protect your data is explained further in the H2O Privacy Notice [HYPERLINK H2O PRIVACY NOTICE]. **If you agree to register with H2O patient network you can activate this choice on the H2O App landing page [HYPERLINK LANDING PAGE]. Please note, if you do not agree to this choice, you will not be able to join and make use of H2O.**

*

→ [Link Back to Landing Page:](#)

*

(B) I agree to share my self reported data with my healthcare provider

The benefits to you of sharing your self reported data with your healthcare provider

H2O can help you share the self reported data that you have collected through the H2O App with your healthcare provider (such as your clinical care team, hospital, general practice or other specialist practices). We expect that sharing your data with your healthcare provider can lead to helpful and useful discussions with them about the success of your treatments and any changes that could be made to further improve your health and quality of life. You can specify which healthcare provider you would like to share this data with. You can indicate your agreement for the H2O App provider to share your self reported data, including your unique H2O code, with healthcare providers that you choose. The healthcare provider is responsible to determine which clinical staff can access your data as part of your health record, when they care for you, in accordance with applicable data protection rules. You can change your selected healthcare provider in the H2O App whenever you wish.

If you agree to share your self reported data with your healthcare provider, you can activate this choice on the H2O App landing page [HYPERLINK LANDING PAGE]. You can disable this choice at any time.

*

Link Back to Landing Page:

IPOP-UP SENTENCE NEEDED ONCE THIS CHOICE IS ACTIVATED:

Click here to select your healthcare provider (If you cannot find your healthcare provider on the list, you will only be able to see your self reported data yourself, and how you compare with the anonymous data on a pool of patients with similar conditions).

*

(C) I would like [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] to ask my healthcare provider to share a copy of relevant parts of my clinical data for [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] to combine with my self reported data

You can ask [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] to collect your clinical data

H2O believes that it is particularly useful for you to be able to view your self reported data over time alongside your clinical data (information about your main conditions, test results and treatments usually in your electronic health records). This allows you and your healthcare provider, for example, to see how effective any change in treatment has been in improving your health outcomes.

The clinical data we recommend to be asked from your healthcare provider, for you to view through the H2O App, is:

- Assessments of your disease, its severity and any complications arising from the disease
- Investigation results such as laboratory tests and radiology investigations (x-rays, scans)
- Medication you have been prescribed
- Other forms of treatment information such as relating to operations, physiotherapy, dietary programmes
- Relevant information on other conditions that you have

You may agree to that the [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] asks your healthcare provider to share [via/ with H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] a copy of your clinical data, for purposes of [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] being able providing you with a combined dataset consisting of your self reported data and your clinical data. Sharing clinical data will depend on your healthcare provider's response to such a request. If you agree to this choice [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] will inform you of your healthcare provider's response of whether they can provide [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] with a copy of your clinical data. [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] may provide you with any relevant updates of your healthcare provider's ability to provide [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] with a copy of your clinical data.

If you wish to ask [H2O and/ or its technical partner [HYPERLINK]] to collect your clinical data you can activate this choice on the H2O App landing page [HYPERLINK LANDING PAGE]. You can disable this choice at any time.

*

Link Back to Landing Page:

[POP-UP SENTENCE ONCE THIS CHOICE IS ACTIVATED:]

Click here to select your healthcare provider

*

(D) I agree that H2O can share my self reported data and my clinical data in a pseudonymized (coded) form with approved researchers and research organizations.

You can permit H2O to enable your data to be used for research, whilst protecting your identity

H2O supports medical and research organizations such as universities, public health agencies, pharmaceutical companies and medical device manufacturers in using health information for scientific research to improve health and healthcare, including to develop new and improved treatments.

In this context, we include a unique patient code number so that different data sources for the same patient can be accurately combined. This coded data is called pseudonymised data. We will only share pseudonymised data with organisations who have obtained adequate prior approval such as from an independent ethics committee and in alignment with the H2O approval process described below. In all cases H2O uses the best available security measures to protect the data while both stored and transferred.

H2O has a strict approval process to ensure that we only work with organisations that access data and conduct research scientifically and ethically, and that your data will only be used to improve the

quality of health and care or to develop better diagnostic and treatment solutions. You can read more about the H2O approval process and the scientific purposes we support (and those that we will always refuse) here: [\[HYPERLINK TO THE H2O APPROVALS PROCESS AND CRITERIA\]](#). On the basis that the research organization fulfils H2O's criteria of authorized research organizations, access is granted to enable:

- more efficient treatment and personalised patient care; development and innovation activities for products or services contributing to public health or social security, or ensuring high levels of quality and safety of health care, of medicinal products or of medical devices;
- activities in the interest of public health (e.g., monitoring, ensuring high level of quality and safety of healthcare, medicinal products or medical devices); activities for reasons of public interest in the area of public and occupational health, such as protection against serious cross-border threats to health, public health surveillance or ensuring high levels of quality and safety of healthcare and of medicinal products or medical devices;
- to produce national, multi-national and Union level official statistics related to health or care sectors;
- EU and national health authorities to carry out their official tasks (e.g. authorisation and supervision of medicinal products); to support public sector bodies or Union institutions, agencies and bodies including regulatory authorities, in the health or care sector to carry out their tasks defined in their mandates;
- scientific and medical research, including development of new treatments and training, testing and evaluation of algorithms, including in medical devices, artificial intelligence systems and digital health applications;
- education or teaching activities in health or care sectors;
- training, testing and evaluating of algorithms, including in medical devices, AI systems and digital health applications, contributing to the public health or social security, or ensuring high levels of quality and safety of health care, of medicinal products or of medical devices;
- providing personalised healthcare consisting in assessing, maintaining or restoring the state of health of natural persons, based on the health data of other natural persons;

Any purpose that might disadvantage individuals, be unethical or only be for profit reasons is prohibited.

H2O also maintains a public list of each time we have provided data to one of these organisations, and why, here: [\[HYPERLINK:\] THE H2O TRANSPARENCY REGISTER](#). We will never reveal whose data has been included, so you will not be able to tell if your anonymised data was included in any of these scientific studies.

National H2O observatories are all connected to the H2O pan-European operating observatory, which enables anonymised data to be analysed at a European level. This European scale covers more patient data and allows more accurate research results to be obtained.

As part of the H2O ecosystem, you can choose that your self reported data and clinical data, in a coded form, may be extracted by the National H2O Observatory or the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider and provided to other H2O-approved organizations to conduct the activities described here. If you agree to the activities described before you will be contacted through the H2O App where an independent ethics committee approval is required to access your self reported data and your clinical data and that you will be provided with an opt-out option to each of these requests. Opting out from one research request will be for such individual request only and you will not lose any benefit of using the H2O App.

If you agree to this choice, you can activate such choice on the [H2O App landing page](#) [\[HYPERLINK LANDING PAGE\]](#). You can disable this choice at any time.

*

[Link Back to Landing Page:](#)

*

(E) Box: Withdrawing my Choices¹

Change your Choices

You are free at any time to change your mind about what you have agreed to. You may disable any (or all) of your choices without giving any reason. You may also add new choices if you find H2O to be useful and have confidence in it.

The withdrawal of all of your choices does not automatically delete self reported data or clinical data already held by H2O up to that time. If you withdraw from H2O no new data will be collected from you or requested from your healthcare provider. You may still keep using the H2O App and collect your self reported data for personal purposes. You can share this yourself with your chosen healthcare provider, through the H2O App or by showing them the data on your H2O App.

Your rights regarding changing your choices is also described in the Section “Your Rights regarding your Personal Data” of the H2O Privacy Notice [[HYPERLINK H2O PRIVACY NOTICE](#)].

Any withdrawal of any your choices will never cause you any difficulty regarding the health care you receive and the relationship you have with your clinical teams.

[\(Link Back to Landing Page\)](#)

Privacy Notice

Welcome to H2O

Thank you for your interest in the Health Outcome Observatory. We, [NAME], are an independent, notfor-profit organization (NGO) located in [COUNTRY, CITY, ADDRESS]. We are part of the crossEuropean H2O network who have been jointly established under the European Horizon 2020 framework for the purpose of drawing together patients, healthcare providers, regulators, and healthcare decisionmakers who share an interest in putting patients at the heart of healthcare. We offer a digitally enabled engagement platform for patients to measure their self reported data whilst enabling control of their own data for personal care and for research purposes. We would like to give you the choice to measure and securely share your self reported data with us to make a positive impact on the health system by improving access to data informing clinical decisions and by providing evidence showing how treatment is working in the ‘real world’. The H2O network is also connected to the H2O pan-European operating observatory, which enables anonymized data to be analyzed at a European level, in addition to the research purposes mentioned in this Privacy Notice and in the H2O Patient Agreement [[HYPERLINK](#)]. This European scale covers more patient data and allows more

¹ **NTD**: Withdrawal features to be made most conveniently accessible on the H2O App, i.e. through as few clicks only.

accurate research results to be obtained.

In our focus on self reported data, we are working to strengthen your voice in healthcare. We are committed through standardising the collection of self reported data to contribute to higher quality and sustainability of care through more transparent evidence of treatment outcomes and information which can benefit public health, discovery and development of medicines and policy making (<https://healthoutcomes-observatory.eu/>) (“H2O”).

When you join the H2O network this does not have any effect or influence on your existing relationship with your healthcare provider (such as your clinical care team, hospital, general practice or other specialist practices) and any informed consent that you may have agreed to separately and independent of H2O.

As outlined in our Terms and Conditions [[HYPERLINK TO H2O SERVICE TERMS](#)], you would not be able to use the H2O App and share your personal data if you are younger than 18 years of age.

The Purpose this Document

The purpose of this Privacy Notice is to inform you about H2O, the objectives we pursue and to explain why we would like to ask for your support. This Privacy Notice complements the H2O Patient Agreement [[HYPERLINK](#)] and which will provide you the opportunity to agree to the collection and use of your personal data for the purposes of H2O. Through the Patient Agreement we would like to explain which permissions we at H2O wish to obtain from you to improve the collection and the sharing of data through H2O.

Through the Privacy Notice we would like to also inform you how we address the security and protection of your privacy and we ensure compliance with applicable privacy and personal data protection laws such as the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

When you join the H2O network this does not have any effect or influence on your existing relationship with your healthcare provider (such as your clinical care team, hospital, general practice or other specialist practices) and any informed consent that you may have agreed to separately and independent of H2O.

The H2O App

The H2O App is provided by a H2O mandated technology provider: [[ADD HYPERLINK](#)] H2O App Provider (H2O App provider). The H2O App may consolidate self reported data and additional data such as from your smartwatches, wearables, or other devices, so you can have a more comprehensive view of your data in one convenient place. You are in control over which data is stored in the H2O App and which data is shared with third parties and people you trust; you can enable and disable the features available in the H2O App at any time.

What Information We Would Like to Collect

Your personal data is information that identifies you or could reasonably be used to identify you. This includes your personal details, such as your name, address, date of birth, your self reported data (such as your current health, the severity and symptoms of the disease you have that is being monitored, your quality of life, such as how active you can be, if you experience pain, have breathlessness, about your appetite, bowel movements, sleep, level of anxiety or distress, the extent to which you are comfortably able to perform your daily activities, tracking any improvements that have occurred through the use of your medication, following operations or other health care treatments you have received and data from your smart watches, wearables, or other of your devices,

or any of your personal preferences) and your clinical data (information about your main conditions, test results and treatments usually in your electronic health records).

With your agreement which you may give through the Patient Agreement [\[HYPERLINK\]](#), H2O and its technical partners [the H2O App [\[HYPERLINK\]](#) provider and/or the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider [\[HYPERLINK\]](#)] may hold the following types of personal data about you:

- Information that identifies you, such as your name, date of birth, address, and contact information such as a telephone number and email address.
- Self reported data that you have collected using the H2O App.
- Your clinical data if you have asked H2O to ask your healthcare provider to share via the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider a copy of your clinical data.

This allows H2O to:

- Use your data in line with the choices you make in the Patient Agreement.
- Communicate with you concerning the H2O App and whenever needed, for example to provide you with important updates.
- To match your self reported data to your corresponding clinical data if you have given permission for H2O to link such data.
- To have a copy of your data so that you can have access to H2O held data wherever you live within Europe.

Your data is not needed for any other purpose. H2O also holds technical data necessary for the use of the H2O App such as technical logs and debug technical information. Please visit the H2O Service Terms for more information here: [\[HYPERLINK TO H2O SERVICE TERMS\]](#).

As highlighted above, joining the H2O network does not have any effect or influence on your existing relationship with your healthcare provider and any informed consent that you may have agreed to separately and independent of the H2O network.

How Your Personal Data will be Used

H2O applies utmost attention to the security and protection of your privacy, and commits to operate in compliance with GDPR, other applicable laws and ethical standards. If you register to use the H2O App to collect your self reported data, you will need to provide permission to H2O for the collection, storage and use of your personal data based on your choices through the H2O Patient Agreement [\[HYPERLINK\]](#). We will collect your personal data as further described herein and we only use your data in line with the choices you make.

When you use the H2O App, H2O through its H2O Server-Side Tech Provider will create a code number for you, which it will use to link your self reported data and copies of your clinical data that you permit us to hold about you, and that is coming from different sources such as other apps collecting your data, different hospitals, clinics and general practices across Europe where you receive care and that hold your clinical data. This unique H2O code number can be used to link your self reported data and clinical data when it is sent to H2O from different places and can be used to respond to future scientific research or health policy queries.

Your unique H2O code number is only disclosed on a need-to-know basis to technology providing companies that you permit to and that can collect self reported data and clinical data from you, such as the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider, the H2O App provider, and technology companies which your healthcare provider use to communicate with you and with H2O. These organisations are only permitted to use your unique H2O code number to connect the systems that communicate with your data in ways that you have authorized, and not to use it for any other purpose. H2O will require all

involved parties to sign a written agreement to protect your personal data and use the personal data only for the purposes as described herein.

The list connecting the code with your name is kept securely by the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider [\[HYPERLINK\]](#).

With respect to transfers to H2O partners such contractors and service providers that H2O engages to support its offering to the H2O patient network and that are located outside of the European Economic Area (EEA), Switzerland and the UK, H2O has entered into specific agreements with these parties to provide appropriate protection for your transferred information where required. A list of partners located outside of your country can be found here: [\[HYPERLINK TO AN ACTIVE LIST OF PARTNERS\]](#).

The safeguards mentioned here is called pseudonymisation, which ensures confidentiality through keycoding your data. In other words, no identification can be made without the list that links your identity to your unique H2O code number. This list will be kept secure and confidential by the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider [\[HYPERLINK\]](#) and will not be shared with or accessed by any other third party. Anonymised data is different from pseudonymised data, it means that it is completely impossible to find the identity of the person from the data at all.

H2O supports medical and research organizations such as, universities, public health agencies, pharmaceutical companies, medical device manufacturers in the large-scale analysis of patient information, to improve health and healthcare, including to develop new and improved treatments. H2O has therefore implemented rules to assess each access request to your self reported data and clinical data for research purposes. H2O carefully checks and approves each organization that asks to analyze your data. On the basis that the research organization fulfils H2O's criteria of authorized research organizations and subject to adequate prior approval such as from an independent ethics committee, access is granted. You can read more about the H2O approval process and the scientific purposes we support (and those that we will always refuse) here: [\[HYPERLINK TO THE H2O APPROVALS PROCESS AND CRITERIA\]](#).

H2O maintains a public register of each of the requests made by research organizations and as approved by H2O. Research organizations will be identified as such, however the public register will contain none of your personal data, all relevant data will be anonymized. The register will be available publicly [\[HYPERLINK:\] THE H2O TRANSPARENCY REGISTER](#).

Legal Basis for Processing Personal Data

H2O will always ask for your consent to the processing of your personal data. Such consent may be withdrawn at any time and without giving any reason by contacting [\[COMPLETE: H2O CONTACT PERSON\]](#).²

Granting such consent does not have any effect or influence on your existing relationship with your healthcare provider and any informed consent that you may have agreed to separately and independent of the H2O network.

² **NTD**: Consider relevance of including other legal bases such as legal obligation or legitimate interests (which would also require a legitimate interests assessment to be made).

What Personal Data will H2O Store and Process?

H2O wishes to store a copy of your self reported data, your clinical data, your unique H2O code, and information on how you are identified by each of the other apps you have used to collect your self reported data and by the healthcare providers you have received care from. By doing so you are then able to change the app that you use, change your healthcare provider that you share data with, for example if you move within your country or to another European country without you losing access to your data. We want to ensure that the data that you have collected over time remains accessible to you wherever you live within Europe.

For this reason, we ask you for a copy of your registration information, your self reported data, your clinical data and your unique H2O code to be held by H2O.

How Your Personal Data will be Protected

We will protect your personal information with utmost care and attention and in accordance with all applicable data protection and privacy laws including GDPR. H2O, the H2O App provider and the H2O Server-Side Tech Provider are responsible for the protection of your personal data, including the pseudonymisation of your personal data, as discussed in Section “How Your Personal Data will be Used”. Based on the permissions you provide to H2O to access your personal data, anyone from H2O or its authorized partners accessing your personal data in a coded form is obligated to respect your privacy and to only use and disclose your personal data for the purposes and in the form, you have agreed to. Your personal data will be protected, using appropriate technical and organizational security measures to safeguard personal data against unauthorized or unlawful access or disclosure and against accidental loss, destruction or damage.

How Long does H2O retain your Personal Data?

H2O will retain your personal data in a coded form for as long as it is needed for achieving H2O objectives, as set out in the beginning of this document, and/or for medical and scientific research. However, H2O will not retain your personal data in coded form for longer than five [5] years after the completion of all such activities, unless H2O is required to keep the data longer by law. After the expiry of the data retention periods, the coded data will be either anonymized and archived or securely deleted.

Your Rights regarding your Personal Data

At any time, you have the right to request access to personal data collected about you. If you believe any of the personal data in your records is inaccurate or incomplete and you can't change such data through the H2O App, you have the right to request the H2O App provider to correct it. To exercise your rights of access or correction, please contact [COMPLETE AS APPLICABLE: E.G. CONTACT PERSON AT THE H2O APP PROVIDER].

In addition, you have the right to request the deletion of any personal data or request the restriction of its use. It may not always be possible to immediately and completely honour your requests (e.g., legal requirement to retain certain data). If your request cannot, or can only partially, be honoured, you will be informed and given the reason(s).

If you have any questions, concerns, or complaints as to how H2O is using your personal data, you may contact [COMPLETE: H2O CONTACT PERSON], who will contact the H2O Data Protection Officer. In addition, the relevant country Data Protection Authority (DPA) is responsible for making sure that privacy law is followed in each European country. For more information about your privacy rights, or if you wish to make a complaint, you can contact your local DPA. A list of European Union supervisory authorities is available here: http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/article-29/structure/dataprotection-authorities/index_en.html.

Your Choices and Permissions for Sharing Your Health Outcome Data

We wish to obtain your permission to collect and share your PROs and patient generated health data through H2O. Granting such permission does not have any effect or influence on your existing relationship with your healthcare provider and any informed consent that you may have agreed to separately and independent of the H2O network.

As we understand that you might like to only make use of some elements of what the H2O App offers, we set out below the separate option for you to choose from which you can then enable and disable at any time on the [H2O App landing page \[HYPERLINK LANDING PAGE\]](#).

As patients' and treatment needs evolve along with the development of the medical science and technology, we may contact you in the future to inform you of potential new ways to collect and analyse self reported data, clinical data and other health data that may require a separate and new patient agreement.

The process for defining outcomes and measures

[Content published in *NEJM Catalyst*]

Stamm TA, Bott N, Thwaites R, Mosor E, Andrews MR, Borgdorff J, et al. **Building a Value-Based Care Infrastructure in Europe: The Health Outcomes Observatory**, *NEJM Catalyst Innovations in Care Delivery*, June 2021. DOI: [10.1056/CAT.21.0146](https://doi.org/10.1056/CAT.21.0146)

Table 1. The final agreed-upon process for defining outcomes and respective measures from the perspective of all relevant stakeholder groups (patients, experts, regulators/authorities and industry). This process is standardized across the disease areas, including identifying generic (cross-cutting) outcomes and measures. It builds on existing outcome standards, such as the ICHOM sets or others, and focuses specifically on the feasibility of implementation and the usefulness of the data. Levels of agreement ranged from 7.5 for starting the more comprehensive endorsement process (patients' rating) to 10 for the Delphi study (regulators' rating) and the consensus conference (patients' rating). The agreement generally increased in the final (third) round, except some which decreased (marked in bold).

Steps of the process for defining outcomes and respective measures	Levels of agreement of patients; experts; regulators/authorities; and industry
<p>Step 1. Establish core team</p> <p>Establish a core team consisting of two chairs (experts in the respective disease area, clinicians and providers; from both the public and/or private sectors), one to two patient representative(s), a methodologist (to oversee the process of defining the core outcome sets), and at least one fellow (to support the activities).</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 8.2; 8.2; 8.0; 8.0</p> <p>3rd Delphi Round: 8.5; 8.5; 9.0; 8.9</p>
<p>Step 2: Identify stakeholders and set up outcomes task force as a wider reference group</p> <p>Identify and include relevant experts from the public and private sectors (clinical, academic, technical, methodological, managerial), representatives/opinion leaders from relevant international health professions and medical/scientific societies, patients with the condition under study (who may not necessarily be familiar with this type of activity), patient advocates, informal caregivers, regulators, members of key Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies, national payer organizations and other relevant stakeholders that have not been listed here. Set up an outcomes task force as a wider reference group composed of selected stakeholders, taking into account diversity, equity and inclusiveness (gender, sociodemographic, geographic, cultural background/ethnicity, etc.), a balance between local and international stakeholders, and representation of all countries in</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 8.5; 8.5; 10.0; 8.6</p> <p>3rd Delphi Round: 8.5; 8.2; 8.0; 9.2</p>

Steps of the process for defining outcomes and respective measures	Levels of agreement of patients; experts; regulators/authorities; and industry
<p>which the core outcome sets will be implemented. Consider a remuneration or compensation for patients and patient representatives.</p> <p>Set up and agree with the task force on general procedures for collaboration, keep a record of the timeframe and meeting dates from the outset to facilitate planning, send regular reminder emails regarding meetings, distribute a slide deck from the previous meeting when informing about follow-up surveys to recall the results of previous discussions, make authorship rules transparent to encourage participation, encourage those not able to attend to provide feedback via email, encourage discussion and highlight areas of ambiguity for clarification, consolidate responses and queries and distribute back to the wider group for feedback prior to the next meeting for discussion. For stakeholders who may be difficult to reach, consider using multiple methods to engage and elicit feedback to ensure inclusiveness. Given the broad range of stakeholders, pay attention to encourage equal participation from all stakeholders and encourage all participants to engage and speak up.</p>	
<p>Step 3. Start endorsement process with relevant other stakeholders</p> <p>Start the process of early dialogue and inclusion of relevant stakeholders for eventual endorsement by the relevant international scientific and professional societies, expert panels/groups, authorities, other relevant projects, as well as patient organizations, who will be key to the acceptability and credibility of the core outcomes sets for clinical, patient and regulatory aspects. Prioritize regions if necessary, but consider worldwide endorsement to increase acceptability, if possible.</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 6.8; 8.4; 10.0; 8.6</p> <p>3rd Delphi Round: 7.5; 8.3; 9.0; 9.2</p>
<p>Step 4: Revisit the existing outcome standards</p> <p>Consider outcomes (domains) and measures separately. Conduct a review according to an international standard, e.g. systematic, scoping, review of reviews or other, or search for an existing systematic review. Look into existing databases of outcomes and outcome measures. If existing, consider also studies on patient perspectives regarding outcomes to include the diversity of their needs. Focus also on levels of adoption, experiences of use, and the value that outcomes data has so far provided to different stakeholders (if this is not published, surveys and qualitative interviews with relevant stakeholders could complement the findings from the literature review). Include patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and other clinical outcome assessments, but also clinical data and biomarkers, if</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 9.0; 8.5; 8.0; 9.4</p> <p>3rd Delphi Round: 8.5; 8.6; 8.0; 9.3</p>

Steps of the process for defining outcomes and respective measures	Levels of agreement of patients; experts; regulators/authorities; and industry
<p>appropriate. Consider item bank approaches and common metrics, where appropriate. Describe overlaps. Consider ongoing projects, current standards for administration of outcome sets and results of pilot studies, if any.</p> <p>Prioritize outcomes and measures according to the feasibility of implementation and the usefulness of the data. Also consider the content included, meaningfulness in clinical decision making and disease management, frequency of use, the context of use, availability, cost of implementation, regulators' requirements and level of acceptance by regulators and HTA bodies, the potential of interoperability, and methodology of development including the level of validation, measurement properties and involvement of all relevant stakeholders, such as patients. Consider outcomes of co-morbidities, if relevant. Consider the language in which different outcome measures are available as this will influence uptake and applicability in different geographies.</p>	
<p>Step 5a. Conduct three-round Delphi exercise (Round 1)</p> <p>Report the results of step 4 to the task force and circulate a list of outcomes, measures and the timing of the assessments in form of an online survey. Ask the members of the task force to comment and add to this if needed; consolidate responses from task force members; include example questionnaires, for those who might be unfamiliar with the tools.</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 8.6; 8.9; 9.0; 8.8 3rd Delphi Round: 8.5; 8.8; 10.0; 9.1</p>
<p>Step 5b: Conduct three-round Delphi exercise (Round 2)</p> <p>Send a revised list with potential additions from the task force members. Ask the task force members to vote on the relevance (includes importance and feasibility) of each outcome, measure and timing of the assessments. Use a scale of 1 to 10, with '1' meaning 'not relevant' to '10' meaning 'extremely relevant' in each group. Consolidate responses.</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 9.6; 9.1; 9.0; 8.9 3rd Delphi Round: 9.5; 8.6; 10.0; 9.1</p>
<p>Step 5c: Conduct three-round Delphi exercise (Round 3)</p> <p>Circulate the group voting results back to the task force members and ask for a new vote in order to achieve a consensus. Show the results separately for patients (including informal caregivers), academia/clinicians, regulators/authorities and industry. Use a consensus threshold of ≥70%. Prioritize patient results for outcomes and timings (50% patients, 30% public experts and 20% industry) and expert results for outcome measures (30% patients, 50% public experts and 20% industry) and use a weighted majority for a final consolidation of results.</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 8.2; 8.5; 7.0; 8.3 3rd Delphi Round: 9.0; 8.5; 8.0; 8.8</p>
<p>Step 6: Hold a consensus meeting and report the core</p>	<p>2nd Delphi Round: 9.4; 8.9; 8.0; 9.0</p>

Steps of the process for defining outcomes and respective measures	Levels of agreement of patients; experts; regulators/authorities; and industry
<p>outcome set</p> <p>Hold a consensus meeting with the outcomes task force to discuss the results of the Delphi process. Give opportunity for virtual participation and consider also asynchronous methods, such as feedback at a later point in time or online consultations. Adapt the core outcome set based on this discussion, if needed, and give appropriate reasons and arguments for potential adaptations. Prepare a scientific manuscript for dissemination together with a lay summary.</p>	<p>3rd Delphi Round: 10.0; 8.9; 9.0; 9.2</p>

[Content included from presentation 'H2O data flows and patient choices for Observatory launch meeting' 07.12.2022]

Figure 1. Initial patient entry into an NO

Figure 2. PRO data sharing with HCPs

Figure 3. Link between PROs and clinical outcomes

Figure 4. Aggregation of data

Figure 5. Secondary use of data

NOTE
The release of patient level data to external research organisations may vary from country to country

Introduction – The vision of H2O

[Content included from a report prepared by Acumen Public Affairs on behalf of H2O]

The Health Outcome Observatories (H2O) represent a collaborative initiative with patients, health care providers, researchers, life-sciences industry, health authorities and regulatory bodies all taking part. With the digital tools (applications) provided by H2O, patients are able to measure their health outcomes in a standardised way. Ultimately, the pseudonymised health data will then be used by patients to track their health; by HCPs to improve treatment decisions; by academia to conduct robust research; by regulators to influence policy and; by developers to address unmet medical needs. Thus, H2O will strengthen the patient voice in health care with the aim of improving outcomes and fostering a value-based approach in healthcare systems. This is the first-ever initiative at scale that collects and incorporates patient outcomes into healthcare decision-making at an individual and population level.

To achieve this vision, we have formed a strategic alliance between the public and private sectors. We intend it to be a catalyst project that stimulates a greater interest in using health outcomes data, including patient-reported outcomes. By that it encourages the adoption of the approach in other countries and other disease areas, and ultimately, improves care and health. The H2O initiative embodies an exciting innovative journey where information on patients' views, experiences and self-reported outcomes are transformed through the Observatories into meaningful, interoperable, and useful data and evidence, fostering innovation in health care in Europe and beyond.

So far, we have set up Observatories in Spain, Netherlands and Denmark with Germany following. We warmly welcome any interested stakeholders to join us in this journey and encourage setting up H2O observatories in their own countries. To facilitate this process, we have interviewed those involved to find the underlying principles that makes setting up H2O observatories a success. This is why we named this paper *H2O in a Box*, as it is meant as a succinct list of the key components required for setting up an H2O observatory in any country and as an elaboration of the key learnings gathered along the way. Here are the five key learnings:

- 1. Initiate the Observatory as a joint mission for all stakeholders**
- 2. Ensure transparency and trust**
- 3. Rely on third-party experts.**
- 4. Learn from others and maintain flexibility** in your approach.
- 5. Leverage your existing network.**

H2O observatories: an ambitious joint mission

H2O is a joint project down to its very core. It joins together stakeholders from all corners of the healthcare world, bringing together academics, doctors, hospitals, patients, and industry all with the aim of achieving better outcomes for patients. Furthermore, it does this across borders, creating a European-wide network and community all fixed on the same aim. It is key to keep this in mind when setting up a new observatory, as this is not an endeavour that is carried out independently, with the true value of the H2O observatory coming from the collaborative effort of all involved.

“It is not the case that you need to find one stakeholder to support. No, you need to find the believers who can see into the future, and value H2O will bring. We have such believers in this project” - Carmen

When building the observatory, one should aim to bring together all these stakeholders. Those who share in the same vision as H2O and are invested from the beginning. They must see the return on

investment that can be gained by collaborating and being committed from the beginning. These key stakeholders will be able to jointly drive forward the initiative. Working together from the get-go ensures no distortion of the goals of the project that one would have been a single stakeholder to take the lead. A team of shared visionaries will see that this comes to be.

“We are invested in building this digital infrastructure. Partners need to know the strength of their investment in H2O, and the ability to make real change for patients” – Matthias

Transparency and trust – principles for collaboration

Transparency and digital health records are intrinsically intertwined. Self-evidently, transparency towards the patients is key. Patients must know exactly how their data is stored, who has access to it and how it is used. H2O has established a patient agreement, in which each individual patient is made aware of the different use of their health data. In this agreement, patients can select the extent to which their (pseudonymised) health data can be used.

“Trust is giving someone power over something that influences you. H2O makes it very clear what agency you have as a patient in the use of your patient data.” - Herko Coomans, digital health policy coordinator at Netherlands Ministry of Health, Welfare, and Sport

However, when we interviewed the key stakeholders, it became evident that transparency has a much broader implication in the setting up of the Observatories, than transparency towards patients alone.

Transparency and collaboration with external stakeholders

In the European sphere, whilst growing, the number of initiatives revolving around PROs and digital health is rather limited. Furthermore, these other initiatives comprise of the key allies that H2O needs to make it a success. Cooperation with the individuals involved in the other projects is important in creating a successful observatory, and to ensure buy-in from the network of individuals working in this field. To this end, it is important to be transparent about H2Os objectives and aims; we have no intent in competing with other initiatives, but rather to join forces and share best practices. Especially considering the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS), H2O is a stern believer in working together for a well-functioning implementation to reap the benefits for all stakeholders. By including many different stakeholder types, you also gain access to compounded expertise and competencies, which further strengthen the foundation of the observatories. In addition to being transparent with patients, we strongly believe it is beneficial to be transparent with external stakeholders to be able to foster fruitful and mutually favourable partnerships.

“H2O is a large consortium of initiatives. It is important to bring existing value and competences together” - Belle de Rooij, Postdoctoral researcher at Integraal Kankercentrum

Transparency and trust within the consortium

Transparency within the Observatories ensures that they are built on a foundation of mutual trust. In order to get broad buy-in within the internal stakeholders, each stakeholder must be made aware of the motivations and agenda of the other stakeholders. In the H2O ecosystem, each stakeholder has something to win, and to ensure that there is mutual trust between the actors, knowing what each other have to gain from the initiative is important.

“You need to start by building trust. The transparent Dutch mentality helped; people have very different priorities and we need to be open about it. Only then you will understand how everyone is approaching the project. We benefitted from the openness to each other.” - Jolanda Koenders, Head of New Product Planning Central Southeast Europe, Takeda

Transparency also entails being honest of your individual role and commitments to the initiative. Other

stakeholders ought to be made aware of the resources and capacities you are willing to dedicate for the project. In large collaborative projects with many moving parts, allocating clear responsibilities to individuals ensures the smooth advancement of the operations. A key learning was to have smaller face-to-face meetings to both foster trust between the stakeholders, and also to ensure that the conclusions from the meetings were actionable.

“Everyone must have a clear role in the consortium, consider dividing the hours needed to work on a given task. It is important to know who you can rely on, and who is involved only in limited capacity”- Belle de Rooij, Postdoctoral researcher at Integraal Kankercentrum

Relying on experts

H2O cannot be done alone. It is a joint endeavour not just between stakeholders within the healthcare communities, but from the business perspective. Setting up a H2O observatory is in practice the setting up of a separate legal entity, and so will need to follow the well-defined practices that are involved in this process. The knowledge needed for doing so falls outside of the remit of expertise that is held by partners of the H2O project. Accordingly, it is essential to establish strong working relationships with the various legal and financial partners one would need.

An understanding of the mission of the observatory and the importance of the governance model to its functioning is paramount to the work in which the legal partners will be involved with. The balance between stakeholders forms the basis of the observatory and must be ensured throughout the framework developed. The equality between stakeholders is what sets H2O apart from other initiatives, with this idea, therefore, needing to be preserved in both documentation and practice. It will be up to trusted legal partners to ensure the checks and balances are in place for this to happen. On-top of this, when onboarding legal partners, they have to be cleared of any existing interests or biases which may shape the approach they take towards the governance structures. As H2O brings together stakeholders from across the health landscape, they will naturally have pre-existing outcomes they wish to see from the observatory. A legal partner tied to closely or directly working for one of these will act accordingly in these interests.

“Having an independent, external lawyer was very important to us. These were deciding criteria in our choice during hiring. We didn’t want the easy option of going with a hospital or industry lawyer” – Jolanda

The same can be said regarding finances. For the success of the observatory, one must cover the basics of any business, and having a strong financial system and knowledge underpinning it is one of these. Working with capable accountants who are able to transparently manage the income and expenditure of the observatory is key. While the observatory works in other areas to ensure better outcomes for patients, it must first ensure that the very basics are covered, with finances being one of these.

Learning from others and being flexible – there is no *one fits all*

Building a H2O observatory is not something that starts off a blank slate. There is a wealth of experience from across Europe that can be leveraged to assist in doing so. Lessons learned from the existing and in-works observatories can be incorporated into the design of a new one, with the necessary adaptations to the national landscape to be made. Ultimately, all H2O observatories are born with the same goal in mind so the overarching ideals and core practices will remain the same. Regardless, it is important to understand that each country has its own legal, political, and cultural differences that must be taken into account when developing a new observatory. Coordinate with those who worked in setting up the previous observatories and follow common steps as much as possible. As stated previously, incorporate in legal and financial experts who know the national

perspective and the needed steps to take.

The Austrian, Dutch, and German observatories have accrued knowledge about how to tailor the observatory to their national setting. In Austria, the observatory will not be a data holder due to questions of liability, but it is stressed that this will solely be the case here but should be kept in mind. In Germany, the nature of the public-private partnership required a clear revenue model and transparency of funding. In the Netherlands, transparency of the goals and funding was similarly required. While such learnings are often country-specific, there are transnational principles that are important to consider and incorporate into a new observatory.

Rely on your existing network

Successful consortiums such as the H2O require driven stakeholders and coordination. It also requires bringing in individuals and institutions that are passionate on the topics of PROs and digital health and understand the gap that the observatories are trying to fill. These consortiums did not emerge from a vacuum, rather, driven individuals leveraged their existing networks and managed to get their networks interested and involved in setting up the Observatories. During the journey of setting up the Observatories, the individuals we interviewed noted that the most powerful method for including other parties in this journey is by making the value proposition of the Observatories abundantly clear. The ultimate vision of H2O is to deliver value-based healthcare and improve patient outcomes; partnering organisation must adhere to these goals.

The Governance model of H2O Observatory is unique and truly the source of its strength; having knowledgeable and competent members comprise the Governance team will facilitate the implementation of the observatory. The strongest governance models are built by individuals who are visionaries, who see the return of investment in their involvement, and understand the societal impact that we are driving for.

“We found so many key allies in the process. We have members representing the Government as well as regulators on our advisory board. The private sector representatives were helpful in driving the project forward and the patient advocacy organisations were very helpful – we meet once a month.” – Linetta Koppert, Oncological surgeon, clinical epidemiologist, MD PhD at Erasmus Medical Center

Conclusion – Building on a strong basis

H2O builds on the collective efforts of stakeholders from all across society. Building an observatory draws on the cumulative knowledge of not only those within the health sphere, but also those from outside it, such as legal and financial experts. Drawing from the expertise of those involved in previous observatories provides a platform to kick-start off, while a clear understanding of the goals, governance, and return on investment can bring in new partners. Led by national visionaries and believers, the stakeholders can drive forward in the creation of a new H2O observatory that takes into account the national landscape with all its legal, political, economic, and cultural sensitivities. With such an alliance in place H2O will strengthen the patient voice in health care and improve outcomes, in turn fostering a value-based approach in healthcare systems.